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**On the systematic position of *Otiorhynchus emrei*
AVGIN & COLONNELLI, 2011**

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Abstract: Based on examination of the holotype, *Otiorhynchus emrei* AVGIN & COLONNELLI, 2011 described originally in the subgenus *Sulcorhynchus* MAGNANO, 1998 is hereby transferred into subgenus *Choilisanus* REITTER, 1912. Such a decision is strongly supported by both external morphology and structure of aedeagus. As a result, the subgenus *Sulcorhynchus* is hereby deleted from Turkish fauna. This group is only distributed in the Western Caucasus.

Key words: *Otiorhynchus*, *Sulcorhynchus*, *Choilisanus*, new placement, Turkey.

INTRODUCTION

Otiorhynchus emrei AVGIN & COLONNELLI, 2011 was originally placed by its authors in the subgenus *Sulcorhynchus* MAGNANO, 1998 even though they recognized the huge distributional disjunction: *O. emrei* was described from Amanos mountains (Nur Dağları) in the very southern Turkey, whereas species of the subgenus *Sulcorhynchus* are known to occur exclusively in the western Caucasus. On the other hand, the subgenus *Choilisanus* has a very wide range of distribution from the Balkans to the Caucasus, including nearly whole Anatolia (parthenogenetic forms excluding). We tried to explain the true systematic position of the discussed species since originally proposed placement seemed from the very beginning dubious.

RESULTS

Subfamily Entiminae

Tribe Otiorhynchini (type genus *Otiorhynchus* GERMAR, 1822)

Genus *Otiorhynchus* GERMAR, 1822 (type species *Otiorhynchus rhacusensis* GERMAR, 1822)

***Otiorhynchus (Choilisanus) emrei* AVGIN & COLONNELLI, 2011 new subgeneric placement**

AVGIN & COLONNELLI (2011) placed their new species in the subgenus *Sulcorhynchus* MAGNANO, 1998 due to two characters: “Even the new species here described is somewhat different from other *Sulcorhynchus* nonetheless we are comprising it in this subgenus since it shows the deep sulcus separating head from the rostrum beneath and the dense vestiture of recumbent scales, which are the main characters allowing recognition of *Sulcorhynchus* among the close subgenera in the arrangement by MAGNANO (1998).” However, these two traits are devoid of any taxonomic significance; sulcus separating head from rostrum ventrally is highly homoplasious character, present in many unrelated subgenera in *Otiiorhynchus*, including *Choilisanus*. The same concerns second trait i.e. type of vestiture. The presence of more or less dense recumbent elytral scales and rows of raised scales arranged into single rows on interstices is so common in *Otiiorhynchus* that it is virtually always devoid of any taxonomic significance. Only quite exceptionally some subtle differences in such a type of vestiture are systematically significant. Already first glance at photographs in the original description allows for a preliminary assumption that it is actually *Choilisanus* and not *Sulcorhynchus* due to large strongly projecting pterygia, which are very typical of the former in contrast to *Sulcorhynchus*, for which small, fairly weakly projecting pterygia are typical. Moreover, pterygia in *Choilisanus* are very thick-walled in contrast to *Sulcorhynchus* which has average, thin-walled pterygia. Moreover, mandibles weakly projecting anteriorly thus weakly visible from above are very characteristic of *Choilisanus*, whereas in *Sulcorhynchus* they are relatively strongly projecting thus well visible in dorsal view. It is worth remembering that deep transversal ventral sulcus between head and rostrum is very typical of *Choilisanus*. It manifests itself in the most spectacular way in *O. (Choilisanus) megapterygius* BIALOOKI, 2016 resembling condition best known in *Mirrorhynchus bellus* MAGNANO, 2003 and in two species representing subgenus *Lixorrhynchus* REITTER, 1914 (BIALOOKI *et al.* 2015). In all of these four species, as well as in *O. emrei*, the ventral sulcus, particularly when viewed dorso-laterally, forms a very deep excision, at most quite inconspicuous in all species of *Sulcorhynchus*, but well-developed in vast majority of *Choilisanus*. *O. emrei* possesses another autapomorphy of *Choilisanus* (absent from *Sulcorhynchus*), namely shallow somewhat irregular longitudinal furrows on basal part of elytra incorporated into mesothorax, normally under prothorax thus invisible.

Although male of *O. emrei* remains unknown, for the sake of completeness it is worth noting that the main difference in the structure of aedeagus between *Choilisanus* and *Sulcorhynchus* is presence of paired well sclerotized/pigmented subapical structures inside pedon in the former and absent from the latter. Female terminalia are similar, differences are very subtle thus rather weakly useful in determination. The most significant, clear-cut difference between the two discussed subgenera consists in general structure of head with rostrum. In *Choilisanus* (Fig. 2) the hind part of the dorsal wall of rostrum (i.e. behind antennal insertions) is gradually expanded from antennal insertions to the eyes, and in one plane with interocular area (thus there is no bridge between lateral wall of rostrum and interocular area), whereas in *Sulcorhynchus* (Fig. 1) the hind part of the dorsal wall of rostrum is subparallel-sided, very narrow ca. one thirds interocular distance, ended in front of eyes, and at angle to interocular area; as a result there is a very wide bridge between lateral wall of rostrum and interocular area.

Although indeed the subgenera of *Otiiorhynchus* are often not precisely defined (their diagnoses are hardly more accurate than these in REITTER 1912) this is not pertinent to the two subgenera discussed; they are well defined, apparently monophyletic lineages and their recognition should pose no problems.

Fig. 1. Head of *Sulcorhynchus* sp.

Fig. 2. Head of *Otiorhynchus (Choilisanus) emrei*.

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